

1 Nano Selenium as antioxidant agent in a multilayer food 2 packaging material

3 Paula Vera^a, Yolanda Echegoyen^a, Elena Canellas^{a,b}, Cristina Nerín^{a*}, María Palomo^c,
4 Yolanda Madrid^c and Carmen Cámara^c

5 ^aAnalytical Chemistry Department, GUIA Group, I3A, CPS, University of Zaragoza, M^a de Luna 3,
6 50018 Zaragoza, Spain

7 ^bSamtack Adhesivos Industriales, C/ Cerámica, nº3, Pol. Ind. Magarola Sud, 08292, Esparreguera,
8 Barcelona (Spain)

9 ^cAnalytical Chemistry Department. Facultad de Ciencias Químicas. University Complutense of Madrid,
10 28040 Madrid, Spain.

11 *Corresponding author. Tel.: +34 976761873;. E-mail address: cnerin@unizar.es

12

13 Abstract

14 Selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) were incorporated in a flexible multilayer plastic
15 material using a water-base adhesive as vehicle for SeNPs. The antioxidant performance
16 of both the original solutions containing spherical SeNPs of 50-60 nm diameter, the
17 adhesive containing these SeNPs and the final multilayer plastic material to be used as
18 food packaging was quantitatively measured. The radical scavenging capacity due to
19 SeNPs was quantified by a free radical assay developed in the laboratory and by the
20 diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) method. DPPH was not efficient to measure the
21 scavenging capacity in the multilayer when the free radical scavenger is not in the surface
22 in contact with it. Several multilayer laminated structures composed by [PET (20µm) –
23 adhesive – LDPE (with variable thickness from 35 to 90 µm)] were prepared and
24 measured, demonstrating for the first time that free radicals derived from oxygen (OH*,
25 O₂* and O₂H) cross the PE layer and arrive at the adhesive. SeNPs remain as such after
26 manufacture and the final laminate is stable after three months of storage. The antioxidant
27 multilayer is a non-migrating efficient free radical scavenger, able to protect the packaged
28 product versus oxidation and extending the shelf life without being in direct contact with

1 the product. Migration tests of both Se and SeNPs to simulants and hazelnuts
2 demonstrated the non-migrating performance of this new active packaging.

3 **Keywords:** antioxidant, free radical scavenger, selenium nanoparticles, multilayer,
4 DPPH, migration.

5

6 **1. Introduction**

7 The profound changes in production, distribution and storage of foods as well as the
8 increased society demand that requires good quality products and longer shelf life, leads
9 to the need of new ideas for the packaging sector. Some of these needs have been satisfied
10 with the use of active packaging, either antioxidant or antimicrobial packaging materials.
11 They are classified in two big groups; scavenging systems or releasing systems. The first
12 one is able to remove oxygen, water, ethylene, free radicals, etc. from the package, thus
13 reducing the oxidation processes or early maturation of the packaged food. The other
14 option releases mainly antimicrobial agents, which are capable to inhibit the microbial
15 growth extending its shelf life. In both cases the system consists of incorporating in the
16 packaging material specific substances, usually called active agents, which will act either
17 as antioxidants or antimicrobials for food [1-8]. Although the idea of having the
18 preservatives in the packaging materials instead of in the food is very attractive, to get
19 these materials is very difficult. There are a series of steps to consider and among them
20 the demonstration of the efficiency is the key point. This faces a new analytical challenge,
21 in which quantitative measurements at high level of sensitivity are required for direct
22 application to a packaging material without previous extraction or dissolution. In this
23 work the efficiency of a new antioxidant material containing Se nanoparticles has been
24 demonstrated.

25 Selenium nanoparticles (SeNPs) can be considered as synthetic antioxidants. Several
26 studies mention their antioxidant capacity [9-12]. SeNPs are able to trap free radicals,
27 increasing their antioxidant effect with decreasing particle size [13,14]. However, all
28 applications and previous measurements were done in direct contact between the SeNPs
29 and the oxidizable matter. Once incorporated into the polymer the homogeneous
30 distribution and size of these SeNPs play a critical role in the antioxidant performance.

1 This means that the evaluation should be applied first to the initial solution used for
2 producing the material, in order to select the best composition, and later to the material.

3 The quantitative measurement of antioxidant properties from a solution involves the
4 application of specific analytical methods, such as oxygen radical absorbance capacity
5 (ORAC) [15,16], or total radical trapping antioxidant parameter trapping (TRAP), or
6 electron transfer as TEAC (trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity) [17-19]. However,
7 none of them can be applied to a packaging material containing nanoparticles, as these
8 methods require the extraction of the antioxidant components to a solution in which the
9 reaction takes place. DPPH was developed by Blois [20]. The assay consists of measuring
10 the scavenging capacity of antioxidants towards a stable free radical (α , α -diphenyl- β -
11 picrylhydrazyl). The antioxidants donate a hydrogen atom and thus, the odd electron of
12 nitrogen atom in DPPH is reduced to the corresponding hydrazine [21]. This specie is
13 considered as a stable free radical because it delocalizes the spare electron over the
14 molecule as a whole and does not dimerize, as happens with the majority of free radicals.
15 This method has been used in plastic materials [22], but it was never applied to
16 multilayers, paper or board where there is not direct contact with the antioxidant agent.
17 In 2008 a new analytical method was developed to measure the antioxidant performance
18 directly in the packaging material without extracting the sample.[23,24]. The method
19 consists of exposing the material to an atmosphere enriched in free radicals. The stream
20 of free radicals passes throughout the material to be evaluated and is carried to a salicylic
21 acid solution, where a chemical reaction takes place. The resulting compounds from this
22 chemical reaction are later analyzed by HPLC with fluorescence detector. This way, a
23 quantitative value of the scavenging capacity is achieved. This method was later
24 automatized and now it allows to simultaneously analyze eight samples, where at least
25 one of them has to be a blank without active compounds. The method measures the radical
26 scavenging properties of the material [25-27] and has been applied before to evaluate the
27 performance of several packaging materials in which the antioxidants were incorporated
28 in the external layer of the packaging. A recent study carried out on a multilayer
29 containing green tea extract in an internal layer of the packaging [28,29] demonstrated
30 that the method is also efficient in this case. But the case of nanoparticles is a particular
31 one, what adds a new challenge to be faced.

32 For this purpose, DPPH and the free radicals method from Pezo were selected to evaluate
33 the antioxidant capacity of multilayers where SeNPs were incorporated. It will be

1 demonstrated for the first time the advantages and limitations of both methods, which will
2 allow to quantitatively measure the radical scavenging capacity of the new antioxidant
3 multilayer containing SeNPs. In addition, the paper demonstrates the mode of action of
4 the non-migrating antioxidant material as free radicals scavenger and opens new doors to
5 further developments in the use of NPs.

7 **2. Materials and methods.**

8 *2.1. Reagents*

9 Sodium salicylate (CAS 54-21-2), 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic acid (2,5-DHB) (CAS 490-79-
10 9), hydrogen peroxide solution (34.01 mg/L), acetic acid (CAS 64-19-7), 2,2-diphenyl-1-
11 picryl-hydrazyl (CAS 1898-66-4) sodium acetate trihydrate (CAS 6131-90-4) and Trolox
12 (CAS 53188-07-1) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Química S.A (Madrid, Spain),
13 all of them had analytical quality.

14 Methanol (high performance liquid chromatography, HPLC grade) was purchased from
15 Scharlau Chemie S.A (Sentmenat, Spain). Purified water was obtained from a Milli-Q
16 185 Plus system from Millipore (Bedford, MA, USA).

17 *2.2. Solutions of Se NPs and samples*

18 SeNPs were synthesized using a solution-phase approach based on the reduction of
19 selenite with ascorbic acid in the presence of different stabilizers agents polysaccharide
20 (chitosan, a Poly(D-glucosamine)) or an ethoxylated non-ionic surfactant (Triton X-100
21 (t-octylphenoxy polyethoxy-ethanol)), isotridecanol ethoxylate and/or 2,4,7,9-
22 tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate. Characterization of the obtained SeNPs by
23 Transmission Electron microscopy showed that the type of agent used for stabilizing
24 SeNPs has a great influence on the size and morphology of the resulting NPs. SeNPs
25 obtained using Chitosan, Triton X100, and 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl 5decyne-4,7-diol
26 ethoxylate were spherical with a diameter size within the range of (20-40), (\approx 100), (18-
27 40) and (28-60) nm, respectively. The use of isotridecanol ethoxylate as stabilizer agent
28 produced NPs with nanorods morphology (data non-shown), which demonstrated poor
29 antioxidant properties.

1 Several solutions containing SeNPs were prepared with a composition detailed in table 1.
2 In order to select the most antioxidant formula, the antioxidant capacity of SeNPs
3 solutions was determined by free radical assay and compared with the same solutions but
4 without NPs (blank solutions).

5 The SeNPs solutions were incorporated into a water-based polyurethane adhesive to
6 manufacture laminates [substrate1-adhesive-substrate2] at laboratory scale. First,
7 different concentrations of SeNPs up to 10% solution of SeNPs were incorporated into
8 the adhesive. Then, it was extended on a 20 x 30 cm substrate (PET of 12 μm thickness)
9 forming a uniform layer using an extender machine (K control coater, RK printcoat
10 instruments). The gramage of adhesive applied was 3 g/m^2 on the laminate, which was
11 gravimetrically controlled. Afterwards, a second 20 x 30 cm substrate of polyethylene of
12 35, 60 or 90 μm thickness, was placed on top of it and the laminate was pressed at 80°C
13 and speed number 4 in a BiO 330 Laminator (made in Korea) forming the laminates
14 shown in table 2.

15 Finally, two laminates with the same composition were thermosealed with a SUPER
16 CELLO (Audion Elektro, Holland) forming a bag of dimensions 1.5dm x1.5dm with inlet
17 and outlet located at 90° to avoid preferential flow ways as well as maximizing turbulence
18 inside the bags, through which the carrier gas enriched with free radicals flow passed.
19 These bags were used to study the influence of the material thickness on the antioxidant
20 capacity, to confirm the mode of action and also for the aging study.

21 For the study of the antioxidant capacity with DPPH, bags of dimensions 1 x 0.5 dm^2
22 were prepared in the same manner.

23 With the aim to discern between selenium endogenous and exogenous from hazelnuts in
24 the migration studies, the synthesis of $^{77}\text{SeNPs}$ was carried out following the same
25 procedure as that applied to the other SeNPs. $^{77}\text{SeNPs}$ solution was incorporated into
26 the adhesive and the built multilayer was used to form the bags filled with hazelnuts and
27 exposed during 10d at 60°C, according to EU legislation 10/2011 [30].

28

29 2.3. *Methods*

30 2.3.1. Free radicals assay

1 In this method (Pezo et al 2006, 2008) [23,24], an atmosphere enriched in free radicals
2 (OH^* , O_2^* and O_2H) carried by an inert gas passes through the active materials and
3 bubbles into a salicylic acid solution. A home-made device was used for this purpose
4 according to the design described in references 7 & 8. Here, a reaction between the not
5 scavenged free radicals and this salicylic acid solution takes place, producing 2,3-
6 dihydroxybenzoic (2,3-DHB) and 2,5-dihydroxybenzoic (2,5-DHB) acids, among other
7 compounds. The major resulting compound, 2,5-DHB, analyzed by high-performance
8 liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled to a fluorescence detector, is correlated with the
9 scavenging properties in such a way that the absence of 2,5-DHB in the solution means
10 that radicals were scavenged by the material.

11 The 2,5-DHB fluorescence signal obtained for each sample was then compared to the
12 reference blank signal. A fluorescent intensity decrease entailed a higher antioxidant
13 capacity of the studied material, because it meant that the material scavenged the free
14 radicals and, therefore, 2,5-DHB was not produced (or it was in a lower extent) in the
15 solution. Then, the antioxidant capacity was indirectly quantitatively evaluated by high-
16 performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) coupled to fluorescence detector where the
17 2,5-DHB produced, as the major reaction product, was determined in the different
18 solutions. The equipment used was a Waters Separation module (Waters, Milford, MA,
19 USA) coupled to a 474 fluorescence detector (Waters, Milford, MA, USA). The
20 chromatographic separation was carried out with a reversed column phase C18 (100 mm
21 long, 4.6 mm i.d and 3 μm particle size) from Waters. The isocratic mobile phase was a
22 mixture of methanol with aqueous acetate buffer (3.5 mmol/L, pH 5.8) with a 10:90 (v:v)
23 at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. The volume injected was 20 μL . Wavelengths of 324 and 448
24 μm were used for emission and excitation measurements respectively.

25

26 2.3.2. DPPH method

27 DPPH method was used for determining the free radical-scavenging activity using a
28 stable free radical (α , α -diphenyl- β -picrylhydrazyl). This compound in methanol solution
29 is deep violet colour and becomes colourless when mixed with a hydrogen atom donator
30 substance, as an antioxidant. This process can be followed by measuring a decrease in
31 absorbance.

1 For this purpose a 100 mg/L solution of DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl) in
2 methanol was prepared and then 10mL of this was added into a 20 mL glass vials which
3 contained either 15 µl of the solutions with SeNPs (table 1) or 0.1 g of the adhesive
4 containing 10% of the solution with SeNPs (table 1). A DPPH solution without SeNPs
5 was used as control.

6 All samples were made in triplicate. Before measuring the absorbance, the vials were kept
7 in the dark to avoid light interaction during 2 or 4 hours of reaction time depending on
8 the antioxidant performance. After that, absorbance at 515 nm was measured by an UV-
9 Vis spectrometer (UV-1700 PharmaSpec, Shimadzu) against a blank solution.

10 The percentage of DPPH inhibition was calculated using the following equation:

$$11 \quad (\text{DPPH_concentration}_{\text{control}} - \text{DPPH_concentration}_{\text{sample}}) * 100 / \text{DPPH_concentration}_{\text{control}}.$$

12

13 2.3.3. Transmission Electronic Microscopy (TEM) and Field emission scanning electron
14 microscopy (FESEM).

15 The size and morphology of the SeNPs incorporated in the water-based polyurethane
16 adhesive were examined by a high resolution Transmission Electronic Microscopy
17 (TEM) (JEOL-2000 FXII) equipped with an X-Ray Energy Dispersive INCA 200 X-
18 Sight of Oxford Instruments with a resolution from 136 eV to 5.9 KeV.

19 The SeNPs incorporated in the laminate at laboratory scale were checked by Field
20 emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) (Carl Zeiss MERLIN™), equipped
21 with a EDS Detector of X-rays scattered INCA 350 of Oxford Instruments with resolution
22 from 127 eV to 5.9 KeV. The sample was prepared coating the PET substrate with the
23 adhesive containing SeNPs and drying it. The second layer of LDPE was not applied to
24 facilitate the FESEM analysis.

25

26 *2.4. Determination of antioxidant capacity for the SeNPs solutions and adhesives.*

27 To study the antioxidant capacity of the SeNPs solutions by free radical assay, the
28 different solutions (table 1) were trapped in eight cartridges made from glass tubes
29 (100mm long, 8mm o.d.; 6mm i.d. inlet; 3mm i.d. outlet) containing silanized glass wool
30 on which the SeNPs solutions were spiked. The cartridges were prepared as follows: glass
31 wool (0.1 g) was inserted into the glass tube to get a bed of 2 cm length, then the desired
32 amount of each SeNPs solution (0.4 grams) was added using a long tip Pasteur pipette to

1 get a complete bed impregnation. The cartridges were installed in the device and the free
2 radicals atmosphere generated passed through them, following the procedure above
3 described.

4 Eight samples were simultaneously analyzed for each assay. Two of them contained only
5 glass-wool as reference samples, three were filled with solutions without SeNPs (blank)
6 and other three replicates with solutions containing SeNPs. The assay was carried out in
7 the conditions above described (section 2.3.1).

8 After 48 hours, 2,5-DHB was determined by HPLC-fluorescence and the antioxidant
9 capacity was expressed as hydroxylation percentage. This was calculated by the following
10 formula: $(2,5\text{-DHB area}_{\text{sample}}/2,5\text{-DHB area}_{\text{reference}})*100$. Therefore, a lower percentage of
11 hydroxylation entailed a higher antioxidant capacity.

12 In addition, to verify the antioxidant capacity of SeNPs solutions with a known
13 antioxidant, this assay was repeated under the same conditions above described, but in
14 this case, with Trolox solutions in methanol at increasing concentrations ($100\mu\text{g/g}$ -
15 $1000\mu\text{g/g}$) to built a calibration plot of the system using Trolox as standard.

16 DPPH was used to study the antioxidant capacity both SeNPs solutions (table 1) and the
17 adhesives with 10% of these solutions.

18 For these purpose $15\mu\text{L}$ of all solutions (table 1) were added into a 20mL vial with DPPH
19 solution and were analyzed according to the conditions described above (section 2.3.2).

20 To complete the study different concentrations of these solutions were prepared ($25\text{-}1000$
21 $\mu\text{g/g}$) and analyzed under the same conditions but in this case centrifugation 4000 rpm
22 for 45 min) and ultrafiltration (Millipore centrifugal filter units, Amicon® Ultra-15.
23 Ultracell 10K, 3500 rpm , 30min) were applied.

24 To study the influence of SeNPs in the adhesive by DPPH, 0.1 grams of adhesive
25 containing 10% of these solutions (table 1) and their respective blanks were placed in a
26 20 ml glass vials and dried on a hot plate for further evaluation. After cooling down, 10
27 ml of DPPH solution were added to each vial and analyzed according to conditions
28 described above (section 2.3.2) together with centrifugation and ultrafiltration tests.

29

30 *2.5. Determination of antioxidant capacity of the laminates.*

1 The type of SeNPs selected and its respective blank were incorporated into the adhesive
2 to manufacture the multilayer plastic bags above mentioned. For each assay, eight bags
3 with the same thickness of LDPE, corresponding to 35 μm , were prepared and analyzed
4 simultaneously. Two out of them were prepared with blank adhesive, lam 0 (reference),
5 three bags were built with adhesive containing 10% of solution without SeNPs (lam 1)
6 and three with adhesive containing 10% of solution of SeNPs (lam 2). This assay was
7 repeated for the different thicknesses of LDPE (60 and 90 μm) in order to study the
8 influence of LDPE thickness on the radical scavenging capacity and to demonstrate that
9 free radicals can diffuse through the LDPE layer. Table 2 describes the composition of
10 each laminate used in the study.

11 Then, several bags of 1 x 0.5 dm², containing SeNPs and the control, were filled with 15
12 ml of the DPPH solution. The bags were placed in 125 mL amber vials to avoid light
13 effect. The percentage of DPPH inhibition was calculated as in section 2.4.

14

15 *2.6. Aging study of SeNPs in the adhesive.*

16 An aging test to evaluate the efficiency of the SeNPs over time was performed. Several
17 mixtures of the adhesive with 10% of the different SeNPs solution and their respective
18 blanks were stored in vials at room temperature, 23°C, and without exposure to light.
19 Approximately every fifteen days, the blank plastic bags and the those SeNPs laminates
20 with 60 μm LDPE (lam 0, lam 3 and lam 4) were evaluated again by the free radical assay.
21 Then, the antioxidant capacity was evaluated and monitored over time.

22 *2.7. Specific migration analysis*

23 Specific migration analyses were carried out with two food simulants as well as with a
24 real food, hazelnuts. Different laminates were prepared as [PET (12 μm) - Adhesive (with
25 and without Se nanoparticles) – LDPE (35, 60 and 90 μm)]. The laminates which
26 contained adhesive without SeNPs were considered as a procedural blank. Bags were
27 built from these laminates, with dimensions 1 dm x 0.5 dm and were filled with 30 ml of
28 food simulant (either EtOH 50% or HAc 3%), or with 10 grams of grinded hazelnuts.
29 Three independent replicates of each sample were analyzed.

1 The assays were made according to the European Regulation 10/2011 EU [30]. The filled
2 bags were introduced in an oven and maintained at 60°C for 10 days. In the case of
3 migration to food simulants an aliquot of each sample was transferred to a glass vial,
4 evaporated in a hot plate at 90°C and redissolved in HNO₃ 1%. The Se concentration in
5 this last solution was measured by ICP-MS. The selected mass of Se was 78. A Se
6 calibration curve in HNO₃ 1% (from 0 to 104.77 ng/g) was prepared from a Fluka
7 selenium standard with a concentration of 988 µg/g. The limit of detection (LOD)
8 calculated as three times the standard deviation of the blank by the slope of the calibration
9 curve was 2.32 ng·g⁻¹.

10 The natural concentration of selenium in nuts and hazelnuts is usually high [31,32]. With
11 the aim to evaluate the possible migration of SeNPs from the multilayer packaging (PET-
12 adhesive+SeNPs-LDPE), ⁷⁷SeNPs were synthesized in order to discern exogenous
13 selenium from the endogenous one already present in the sample. Endogenous content of
14 selenium in hazelnuts was 120 µg·Kg⁻¹ on hazelnuts under study. ⁷⁷SeNPs were
15 synthesized and laminates were produced in the same manner as for the rest of migration
16 studies. The possible migration of ⁷⁷SeNPs incorporated into the packaging from bags to
17 hazelnuts was also evaluated by ICP-MS. After the storage in the packaging with different
18 LDPE thicknesses under the conditions previously mentioned, an aliquot of 500 mg of
19 hazelnut sample was digested with concentrated HNO₃ (Merck) and 30% hydrogen
20 peroxide (Panreac) (5:1 v:v) in double walled advanced composite vessels (ACV), using
21 a 1000 W microwave sample preparation (MS) microwave oven (CEM, Mattheus, NC).
22 The resulting solution was diluted with deionized water and ⁷⁷Se was determined by ICP-
23 MS. Moreover, samples on packages without ⁷⁷SeNPs were also used as control. The
24 results are expressed as the mean value (standard deviation for n=3) (LOD ≈ 0.46 ng
25 Se·ml⁻¹ and LOQ ≈ 1.53 ng Se·ml⁻¹)

26

27 **3. Results and Discussion**

28 The principle of antioxidant behavior in this work is based on free radicals scavenging,
29 following the theory described by C. Nerín [33]. SeNPs incorporated in the adhesive are
30 non-migrating free radical scavengers and consequently they act as good antioxidants, as
31 will be demonstrated. First, the antioxidant capacity for SeNPs solutions and adhesives
32 containing SeNPs with different stabilizing agents was tested by both the DPPH and free

1 radical assays. The solution providing the maximum antioxidant capacity was
2 incorporated into the adhesive. This active adhesive was later used to build the multilayer
3 (laminates) of different thicknesses. This way SeNPs were incorporated in the adhesive
4 applied on the internal layer of the laminate. Consequently, the scavenging properties
5 imply that the free radical cross the LDPE layer and arrive at the adhesive layer, where
6 they can be scavenged by the SeNPs. To demonstrate this mode of action several
7 laminates with increasing thicknesses of LDPE layer were tested. Fig. 1 confirms that the
8 radical scavenging capacity decreases when the thickness increases. Diffusion through
9 the LDPE layer of oxo, hydroxo and peroxy radicals is efficiently achieved and then these
10 free radicals arrive at the adhesive behind the LDPE layer and are scavenged. This
11 behavior is not surprising. Diffusion coefficients of many organic compounds throughout
12 LDPE layer have been measured in several papers [34-36] and it has been demonstrated
13 that diffusion of organic molecules in LDPE are usually very fast. Of course this diffusion
14 depends on the molecular mass and volume and also on the polarity of the specific
15 molecule. But the main variable affecting is the size of the molecule. The case of small
16 radicals such as OH^* , O_2^* and O_2H^* is even faster, although the corresponding diffusion
17 coefficients were never measured. The experimental data showed that in fact these
18 radicals cross the LDPE and arrive at the adhesive layer where the nanoSe is anchored.
19 When increasing the thickness of LDPE the diffusion takes more time and some of the
20 free radicals are probably lost, what results in decreasing the scavenging capacity.
21 However, when the free radicals are big, such as that of DPPH^* , they cannot cross the
22 LDPE layer, as demonstrated in this study. Although the antioxidant performance of
23 SeNPs has been demonstrated by other authors [9-12] this is the first time that the
24 behavior of nanoparticles without direct contact with the free radicals has been
25 demonstrated. The stability of the SeNPs over time was examined as well. Both studies
26 were carried out by free radical assay and DPPH method and the results are shown below.

27 *3.1. Determination of antioxidant capacity for the SeNPs solutions and adhesives.*

28 3.1.1. Free radical assay

29 Four solutions (1 to 4) containing 100 mg.L^{-1} SeNPs synthesized in presence of different
30 stabilizing agents were used to evaluate the scavenging capacity by the DPPH and free
31 radical assay and the results were compared to those of the respective control.

1 The results obtained by the free radical assay are shown in Figure 1, where the antioxidant
2 capacity is expressed as % hydroxylation. Clean glass-wool without any solution was
3 used as blank reference (100% hydroxylation when there is not antioxidant capacity), and
4 the rest were the solutions with or without SeNPs. A decrease of hydroxylation % is
5 correlated to an increase of antioxidant capacity [24].

6 Those solutions without SeNPs demonstrated to have certain antioxidant capacity, which
7 can be attributed to the capacity as scavengers of free radicals of the reagents used in the
8 synthesis of SeNPs used as well as control samples..

9 Only solution 4, among the four solutions containing 100 mg.L⁻¹ SeNPs, showed
10 significant differences compared to the respective blank. Its hydroxylation percentage
11 was lower than the control (53 % vs 70 %), so its antioxidant capacity was higher. This
12 result demonstrates that the 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate, reagent
13 used to stabilize the SeNPs solution, was the most appropriate stabilizer. This percentage
14 of hydroxylation (53%) corresponds to 500µg/g of Trolox in methanol.

15 Taking into account this positive result, higher concentrations of SeNPs, 750 and 1000
16 mg.L⁻¹(solutions 5 and 6), were tested (Figure 1). The fact that an increase of SeNPs did
17 not provide, as expected, an enhance of its antioxidant capacity was attributed to the
18 limited concentration of 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate, as it was the
19 same as that used for 100 mg.L⁻¹ Se NPs, which was not enough for a complete SeNPs
20 stabilization.

21 Thus, the percentage of 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate in the solution
22 of 1000 mg.L⁻¹ was increased to 1% (solution 7 and 8) and 7 % (solution 9 and 10) at two
23 different pHs. The results obtained, also shown in Figure 1, evidenced that the solutions
24 with a higher percentage (7%) of stabilizing agent (solutions 9 and 10) provided very
25 encouraging results, as the hydroxylation percentage decreased to 14 and 19% for 1 and
26 7% respectively. These results demonstrated that SeNPs act as very good antioxidant
27 agents when nanoparticles are well established.

28 The non-migrating concept applied to SeNPs in this paper has been demonstrated by
29 specific migration analysis with both food simulants and real food (hazelnuts), using ⁷⁷Se
30 to produce the SeNPs in the case of migration to hazelnuts and ICP-MS as analytical
31 technique. The details of this study are shown below.

1

2 3.1.2. DPPH Method

3 The antioxidant capacity of all the above mentioned solutions and adhesive containing
4 SeNPs was tested (alone and once incorporated in the adhesive) by the DPPH method.
5 However, the results obtained were not coherent with those previously obtained by the
6 free radical assay. For both the solutions and the adhesives, DPPH inhibition of the blank
7 was higher than that of the solution or the adhesive with SeNPs. Also, as SeNPs
8 concentration increases, the percentage of DPPH inhibition increases, and so, the
9 antioxidant capacity. The results obtained for solutions with different concentrations of
10 SeNPs prepared from solution 9 and its respective blank are shown in Figure 2a. In
11 addition to the mentioned lower antioxidant capacity for higher concentrated solutions,
12 the standard deviation of the three replicates was high. Similar results were obtained for
13 solutions with different concentrations prepared from solutions 7, 8 and 10.

14 One possible explanation is that the nanoparticles interfere with the measurement in the
15 spectrophotometer producing light scattering effect. Consequently, the absorbance at 515
16 nm will be higher than that expected. If this happens, the measured concentration of
17 DPPH will be higher than the real one, thus creating an optical interference.

18 Two strategies were applied to avoid this problem: centrifugation (4000 rpm for 45 min)
19 and ultrafiltration of the solutions (Millipore centrifugal filter units, Amicon® Ultra-15.
20 Ultracell 10K, 3500 rpm, 30 min) in both cases after the reaction time.

21 The results obtained by centrifugation were not successful but after ultrafiltration and
22 removal of the SeNPs from the solution, the results obtained were coherent with those
23 obtained by the free radical assay (Figure 2b), and the antioxidant capacity of the
24 adhesives increased with increasing SeNPs concentration, as expected. Also, the lower
25 standard deviation between the three replicates confirmed the previous hypothesis. These
26 results indicate that the DPPH method is not suitable for the analysis of antioxidant
27 capacity of solutions containing nanomaterials in a single step, while the presence of
28 nanoparticles does not interfere with the free radical assay.

29 A concentration of 100 mg.L⁻¹ of SeNPs in the adhesive was selected as the optimum. In
30 addition, previous studies of compatibility with the adhesive established 10% as the
31 maximum amount of solution that can be added to the adhesive without losing any

1 adhesion capacity. The antioxidant capacity of the adhesives prepared with the different
2 solutions in which 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate is used as stabilizing
3 agent, after ultrafiltration, are shown in Figure 2c. In all cases, adhesives prepared with
4 blank solutions presented some antioxidant capacity. No significant differences in
5 antioxidant capacity were found between the solutions prepared with different
6 concentrations of stabilizing agent or at different pHs. The antioxidant capacity was
7 slightly higher for the adhesive prepared with solution 7. However, according to the
8 results obtained by the free radical assay, solution 9 was selected as the optimum one to
9 continue with the rest of the study and manufacture the laminates.

10

11 *3.2. Antioxidant capacity of the laminates and influence of LDPE thickness.*

12 Once the solution with the highest antioxidant capacity (solution 9) was selected, an
13 antioxidant water-base polyurethane (PU) adhesive with 10% of solution 9 and its
14 respective blank was prepared. Laminates with different LDPE thicknesses (35, 60 and
15 90 μ m) were tested, as described in section 2.2, and their antioxidant capacity was
16 evaluated by both the free radical assay and DPPH method.

17 Figure 3 shows the % hydroxylation (lam 0 as reference=100%) together with the
18 different laminates (see Table 2 for description), with and without SeNPs. As can be seen,
19 the blank laminates (without SeNPs) possess a certain antioxidant capacity because the
20 percentages of hydroxylation of lam 1, 3 and 5 were lower than those of laminate 0 (used
21 as reference). This result is in good agreement with that obtained for the blank solutions
22 without SeNPs, (section 3.1.1), and is attributed to the presence of some antioxidant
23 compounds, different from SeNPs, in the composition.

24 A TEM photograph of SeNPs in the adhesive was obtained (Figure 4), where spherical
25 nanoparticles can be clearly seen. The X ray spectrum identifies the Se in the
26 nanoparticles as shows Figure 4.

27 Furthermore, the hydroxylation percentage decreases when the thickness of LDPE layer
28 decreases (lam 2 < lam 4 < lam 6). This behavior demonstrates for the first time that the
29 free radicals from oxygen (OH*, O₂* and O₂H), which have a molecular mass between
30 17 and 33 amu, are able to cross the LDPE layer and diffuse through it, arrive at the
31 adhesive where SeNPs were inserted and be scavenged when thin LDPE layers are used.

1 The percentage of DPPH inhibition obtained (not shown) was very similar for all the
2 laminates studied and no significant differences with the adhesive with and without
3 SeNPs or with a bag of 60 μm or 35 μm LDPE were observed. The large size of DPPH
4 with a molar mass of 394.32 g/mol, prevent its diffusion through the LDPE layer and so
5 its penetration to reach the layer of adhesive behind the LDPE layer, where the SeNPs
6 were placed. This performance opens new doors to the concept of antioxidant as radical
7 scavenger, in which the molar mass of free radicals can be a limiting factor when no direct
8 contact occurs. However, it can be pointed out that the oxidation process starts from the
9 free radicals derived from oxygen. Other organic free radicals, such as lipid and lipid
10 peroxy radicals, are formed from the reaction between the lipids and those free radicals
11 derived from oxygen. However, the early free radicals initiating the oxidation reaction
12 are always those derived from oxygen. Lipid and lipid peroxy radicals can be considered
13 as secondary initiators, probably part of the propagation step in the oxidation reaction.
14 Consequently, the oxidation protection can be achieved just using the scavengers for
15 oxygen derived species. In this case, the lack of direct interaction between SeNPs-DPPH
16 justifies the negative response given by DPPH. Thus, it can be confirmed that the DPPH
17 method is not suitable for measuring the antioxidant capacity in multilayer materials
18 where the radical scavenger is not in direct contact with the reagent. It is important to
19 point out that it is the first time that this limitation of DPPH method is reported.

20

21 *3.3. Aging study of SeNPs in the adhesive.*

22 Once the antioxidant capacities of the SeNPs applied to the laminates were confirmed,
23 the stability of the adhesives over time was evaluated. This is a critical and important
24 feature for further industrial use, due to the elapsed time from their production to their
25 final end-user application to prepare the new manufactured antioxidant food packaging
26 materials

27 Samples prepared with the new antioxidant adhesive with SeNPs or blank solutions were
28 stored and analyzed at approximately fifteen days intervals. It was observed that SeNPs
29 sedimented with time at the bottom of the vial being within thirty days, most of them
30 already deposited at the bottom. Therefore, the vial was sonicated for approximately 30
31 minutes to obtain a homogenous adhesive sample before application. Laminates of 60 μm
32 LDPE thickness were then manufactured and analyzed by free radical assay.

1 Figure 5 shows the results of antioxidant capacity obtained at the different storage times.
2 As can be observed, the percentages of hydroxylation for lam 4 increased from 40% to
3 90% over time, which evidences a considerable decrease in antioxidant performance.
4 These results showed a close relationship between the decrease in antioxidant capacity of
5 SeNPs laminates and the sedimentation of nanoparticles. After 62 days, the percentage
6 of hydroxylation found for lam 4 was 90%, similar to that obtained with the blank, so the
7 SeNPs were not anymore in the adhesive and thus the antioxidant capacity was
8 completely lost. This may be due to an agglomeration of the SeNPs with time, not even
9 able to separate into individual nanoparticles after sonication. This result can be very
10 useful for the suppliers of these materials as it is advised not to keep the adhesive
11 containing SeNPs stored longer than one month.

12 The aging process of the laminate once produced with SeNPs was also studied. As can be
13 seen in Figure 5, the laminates were stable for three months, what emphasizes the
14 importance of this development.

15 Also, a FESEM photograph of SeNPs in the laminate is shown (Figure 4), where can be
16 seen that SeNPs are distributed in the material retaining their original shape and size.

17

18 *3.4. Migration studies*

19 The results obtained in the migration tests to food simulants showed that in all cases the
20 migration of ^{78}Se was below the LOD. When migration tests were done in hazelnuts and
21 ^{77}Se was measured, the results on the ratio $^{77}\text{Se}/^{78}\text{Se}$ on hazelnuts packaged in the new
22 antioxidant material and those packaged in blank material (without SeNPs) were similar
23 and no significant differences were found between controls (samples contained in a
24 packaging without SeNPs) and active packaging with $^{77}\text{SeNPs}$ incorporated. Moreover,
25 the material thickness did not influence the SeNPs migration in any case. Thus, migration
26 of SeNPs was not observed from multilayer packaging to food or food simulants after the
27 migration assays at 60°C for 10 days. This was expected, as the SeNPs were anchored
28 behind the LDPE layer in the multilayer material and the nanoparticles cannot diffuse in
29 the non-polar LDPE layer [37]. If the nanoparticles were incorporated directly in the
30 LDPE layer some low migration could be expected, as has been demonstrated in previous
31 publications working with silver nanoparticles or nanoclay [38-41]. However, only the

1 nanoparticles from the surface migrate either to the simulants or to the food. The
2 additional advantage of this development, where the nanoparticles are not in direct contact
3 with the food, but behind the LDPE layer, is that they cannot migrate. This way, we can
4 guaranty that the material is safe. The same behavior has been demonstrated working with
5 green tea extract anchored in the adhesive behind the LDPE in a multilayer structure [29].

6

7 **4. Conclusions**

8 The antioxidant capacity based on the capacity of SeNPs as free radicals scavengers has
9 been demonstrated. SeNPs were stabilized and incorporated for the first time in an
10 adhesive, further used for building a multilayer plastic structure of PET-adhesive-LDPE.

11 The antioxidant performance of this multilayer has been studied by both the DPPH
12 method and the free radical assay previously developed [23,24]. The study concludes that
13 DPPH radical is not able to cross the LDPE layer and consequently the DPPH method is
14 not valid for measuring antioxidant capacity when the antioxidant is not in direct contact
15 with the DPPH radical. This behavior could be attributed to the big size of DPPH radical,
16 that is not able to diffuse throughout any plastic layer. It is the first time that such a
17 limitation of the method is described. In addition, when nanoparticles are involved in a
18 solution, DPPH method also shows some spectral interferences, which require
19 ultrafiltration and/or dialysis to remove the nanoparticles from the solution. This
20 drawback was never described before.

21 The thicker the laminate the lower the antioxidant capacity of the material because free
22 radicals (OH^* , O_2^* and O_2H) are able to cross more easily thinner laminates of the LDPE
23 layer and efficiently scavenged when reaching the adhesive containing SeNPs. This
24 behavior is demonstrated in this work.

25 Concerning the SeNPs it has been demonstrated that among the stabilizing agents tested
26 7% of 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate at pH 3 is the most appropriate for
27 this application. An increase of nanoparticles concentration also produced an increase in
28 the antioxidant capacity of both the solutions and the adhesives, and so, 100 mg.L^{-1} was
29 selected as the optimal concentration in the adhesive. Higher concentration caused a
30 reduction of the adhesion properties.

1 The adhesive containing SeNPs is stable for one month, after which and even using
2 sonication the antioxidant capacity is not recovered, probably due to an irreversible
3 aggregation of nanoparticles.

4 It is important to mention that no migration of SeNPs was found from the laminates to
5 food simulants or real food inside the package.

6 Finally it is worth pointing out that SeNPs were placed between PET and LDPE in the
7 laminates here studied. The study demonstrates that free radicals (OH*, O₂* and O₂H)
8 cross the PE layer, but this is unlikely happens with PET, what makes possible the long
9 lasting of the laminates, as the SeNPs remain unchanged in the laminate.

10 Many food applications could benefit from this new antioxidant material, as its
11 mechanical, optical and machinability performance are exactly the same as those usually
12 required for any application. Then, fresh meat, ready to eat, dried nuts, snaks and
13 everything susceptible of oxidation can be packaged with this new material. Transparency
14 and color are not compromised and the SeNPs are neither visible, nor perceived.

15

16 **Acknowledgement**

17 Authors wish to thank the financial support from the Ministry of Economy and
18 Competitiveness (Spain) (Project IPT-2012-0261-420000), Gobierno de Aragón and
19 European Social Funds given to GUIA group T-10 (University of Zaragoza) and
20 SAMTACK Industrial Adhesives (Barcelona).

21

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8

Table 1: Composition of the solutions with SeNPs studied.

Solution number	Se NPs concentration	Stabilizing agent	Concentration of stabilizing agent
1	100 ppm	Chitosan	0.1%
2	100 ppm	Triton X-100	0.1%
3	100 ppm	isotridecanol ethoxylate	0.1%
4	100 ppm	2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate	0.1%
5	750 ppm	2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate	0.1%
6	1000 ppm	2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate	0.1%
7	1000 ppm	2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate	1% (pH 3)
8	1000 ppm	2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate	1% (pH 6.5)
9	1000 ppm	2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate	7% (pH 3)
10	1000 ppm	2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate	7% (pH 6.5)

Table 2: Different laminates studied.

Laminate number	Substrate 1	Solution added to Adhesive	Substrate 2
0	PET (12 μm)	-	PE (different thicknesses)
1	PET (12 μm)	10% solution 9 blank	PE (35 μm)
2	PET (12 μm)	10% solution 9	PE (35 μm)
3	PET (12 μm)	10% solution 9 blank	PE (60 μm)
4	PET (12 μm)	10% solution 9	PE (60 μm)
5	PET (12 μm)	10% solution 9 blank	PE (90 μm)
6	PET (12 μm)	10% solution 9	PE (90 μm)

Table 3: Migration results of ⁷⁸SeNPs for food stimulants and ⁷⁷SeNPs for grinded hazelnut measured by ICP-MS

Samples	Concentration of ⁷⁸ Se		Concentration of ⁷⁷ Se
	Simulant EtOH 50%	Simulant HAc 3%	10 grams of hazelnuts
Laminate PET (12 μm) /adhesive with SeNPs/ PE (35μm)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Laminate PET (12 μm) /adhesive with SeNPs/ /PE (60μm)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Laminate PET (12 μm) /adhesive with SeNPs/ /PE (90μm)	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD

LOD for ⁷⁸Se = 2.32 ng/g.

LOD for ⁷⁷Se = 0.46 ng/ml.

Figure 1: Antioxidant capacity expressed as % hydroxylation for the solution with or without Se NPs synthesized with different stabilizing agents and with different conditions.

Figure 2b: Results of DPPH inhibition obtained for adhesives with different concentrations of SeNPs prepared from solution 9 after ultrafiltration.

Figure 2c: Antioxidant capacity (expressed as % DPPH inhibition) for the adhesives prepared with the solutions with 2,4,7,9-tetramethyl-5decyne-4,7-diol ethoxylate as stabilizing agent, after ultrafiltration.

Figure 3: Antioxidant capacity expressed as % hydroxylation for the laminates with or without Se NPs for different thickness.

TEM photograph of SeNPs incorporated in the adhesive

ESEM photograph of SeNPs in the laminate

Figure 4: TEM photograph of SeNPs incorporated in the adhesive with their compositions on the top and a FESEM photograph of SeNPs in the laminate with their compositions on the bottom

Figure 5: Antioxidant capacity expressed as % hydroxylation for the laminates with PE 60 μm in the ageing test